

**“CORRELATION BETWEEN EPS AND DPS OF SELECTED AUTO COMPANIES
IN INDIA: AN EMPIRICAL RESEARCH”**

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Abstract

Increasing importance of financial planning decision making i.e. financing, investment, and dividend in a company has been widely discussed among recent research. The present study is focusing on issues related with correlation between earning and dividend pattern of various companies in auto industry in India included in NSE NIFTY. The researcher uses correlation as a statistical tool to find out the relation between EPS and DPS.

Key words: Earnings per share, dividend per share.

INTRODUCTION

An earnings per share (EPS) is a commonly used phrase in the financial world. Earnings per share represent a portion of a company's profit that is allocated to one share of stock. It is the total earning divided by the number of shares in issue. It shows how much of the company's profit, after tax, each shareholders owns. No doubt, one of the most important policies in corporate financing is the dividend policy. This is not only from the viewpoint of the company, but also from that of the shareholders, the consumers, the workers, the regulatory bodies and the government. The relative importance of this policy stems from the fact that it is a pivotal policy around which other financial policies rotate, hence central to the performance and valuation of firms (Bebczuk, 2004). A firm's dividend policy refers to its choice of whether to pay out cash to shareholders, in what fashion, and in what amount. The most obvious and important aspect of this policy is the firm's decision whether to pay a cash dividend, how large the cash dividend should be, and how frequently it should be distributed. In a broader sense, dividend policy also encompasses decisions such as whether to distribute cash to investors via share repurchases or specially designated dividends rather than regular

dividends, and whether to rely on stock rather than cash distributions. Non-traditional forms of dividend payments, especially share repurchases are much more commonly used today, and so the dividend decision is much more complex and difficult than in the past. Also, there are many more important categories of shareholders who must be satisfied today—especially institutional investors—whereas managers once merely had to satisfy individual stockholders. An increase in the dividend payout is considered to be good news. The firm is demonstrating that it not only has positive cash flows, but these cash flows are increasing enough to justify a higher payout to shareholders. The firm “proves” its cash flow by paying out some of that cash to its shareholders. Higher dividends may signal permanent higher earnings for the firm. Dividend announcement by a company is an indicator to shareholders. Basically, managers and shareholders have different information, where managers have more complete information than shareholders. The shareholders will interpret the increase in dividend payments by the company, as the indicator that management has a high cash flow forecast future. Conversely, the decline in dividend payments interpreted as anticipation of the limited cash flow in the future. Lintner (1956) advocated the view that firms increase dividend payments only if the management believes that these high dividend payments can be maintained in the future. The decision to establish a stable cash dividend is, as any other decision making, influenced by the environment of and the context of such decision. The tendencies in cash dividend policy are not only influenced by internal factors such as investment opportunity, profitability and liquidity of companies, but also, influenced by external factors (Jensen & Johnson, 1995; Jensen & Smith, 1984; Lintner, 1956). The uncertainty with respect to the world-wide policy, growth, macroeconomic problems, stability, technology and changes in consumers tastes influences managers’ decision making (Roberto, 2002). Available information in the financial markets reduces the uncertainty and leads to better decisions about the company’s performance.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the present study are:

- (i) To determine the performance of auto companies included in NSE NIFTY as per EPS and DPS
- (ii) To find out the correlation between earning per share and dividend per share of auto companies included in NSE NIFTY

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

For this empirical analysis, data has been collected from the share broking sites and selected auto companies' financial reports. The researcher has taken all the auto companies which are included in NSE NIFTY. The researcher found 6 auto companies viz;

1. Bajaj Auto
2. Tata Motors
3. Eicher Motors
4. Hero Motocorp
5. Mahindra and Mahindra
6. Maruti Suzuki India

The data related to Earning per Share and Dividend per Share of six auto companies has been taken for five years viz; 2015 to 2019.

The researcher used the following statistical tools such as:

- (i) Mean
- (ii) Pearson Correlation

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The analysis and interpretation of the study are mentioned in the following tables and figures:

Table 1: Earning per share and Dividend per share of auto companies

S. No.	Name of the Companies	Variables	March 2019	March 2018	March 2017	March 2016	March 2015
1	Bajaj Auto	EPS	161.57	140.59	132.27	135.80	97.24
		DPS	60.00	60.00	55.00	55.00	50.00
2	Tata Motors	EPS	5.95	-3.05	-7.15	-0.18	-14.72
		DPS	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.20	0.00
3	Hero Motocorp	EPS	169.47	185.13	169.11	156.86	119.47
		DPS	87.00	95.00	85.00	72.00	60.00
4	Eicher Motors	EPS	753.02	628.46	573.32	482.02	206.21
		DPS	125.00	110.00	100.00	100.00	50.00
5	Maruti Suzuki India	EPS	248.30	255.62	243.32	177.58	122.85
		DPS	80.00	80.00	75.00	35.00	25.00
6	Mahindra and Mahindra	EPS	38.58	35.04	58.66	51.60	53.47
		DPS	8.50	7.50	13.00	12.00	12.00

Source: money.rediff.com

The average EPS and DPS for five years of Auto Companies are mentioned herein below:

Table 2: Average of EPS and DPS of Auto Companies

S. No.	Name of the Companies	Variables	Average
1	Bajaj Auto	EPS	133.494
		DPS	56.00

2	Tata Motors	EPS	-3.83
		DPS	0.04
3	Hero Motocorp	EPS	160.008
		DPS	79.80
4	Eicher Motors	EPS	528.606
		DPS	97.0
5	Maruti Suzuki India	EPS	209.534
		DPS	59.0
6	Mahindra and Mahindra	EPS	47.47
		DPS	10.60

The correlation is found between earning per share and dividend per share of different auto companies. The results are mentioned herein below:

Table 3: Degree of Correlation between EPS & DPS

S. No	Name of the Companies	Correlation
1	Bajaj Auto	0.918
2	Tata Motors	0.263
3	Hero Motocorp	0.967
4	Eicher Motors	0.982
5	Maruti Suzuki India	0.976
6	Mahindra and Mahindra	0.994

FINDINGS

After going through the above study, the researcher presents the following findings:

- 1) The highest average EPS among auto companies under study is of Eicher Motors. Also it pays average DPS which is also highest.
- 2) The average EPS of Tata Motors is negative however it pays DPS of Rs 0.2 in the year 2016 which is lowest among the auto companies included in NIFTY.
- 3) EPS of Tata Motors is negative from 2015 to 2018 therefore it does not paid any dividend during these years except in the year 2016
- 4) EPS of Mahindra and Mahindra has dropped hugely during 2018 and 2019 as compared to other previous years; accordingly it dropped DPS also for these two years.
- 5) Out of 6 auto companies Hero Motocorp and Maruti Suzuki India experienced a lower EPS in the year 2019 as compared to the year 2018.
- 6) Out of 6 auto companies the DPS of Hero Motocorp dropped in the year 2019 as compared to the year 2018.

- 7) There is always a link between earning per share and dividend per share as dividend is generally paid to the owners out of the earnings of the company.
- 8) There is a perfect correlation between EPS and DPS of Mahindra and Mahindra.
- 9) There is nearly perfect correlation between EPS and DPS of Eicher Motors.
- 10) There is a very high degree positive correlation between EPS and DPS of Bajaj Auto, Hero Motocorp, Maruti Suzuki India.
- 11) There is a low degree positive correlation between EPS and DPS of Tata Motors. The company is not paying any dividend during the last three years.

CONCLUSION

It can be said that companies belonging to auto industry have declared dividend does follow a similar pattern in giving dividends to shareholders in relation to the earnings except Tata Motors.

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